

Review the challenges associated with hydrogen-based vehicles and recent advancements

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Introduction

- ❖ A hydrogen fuel-cell vehicle uses the same kind of electric motor to turn the wheels that a battery-electric car does.
- ❖ It's powered by a fuel-cell stack in which pure hydrogen (H_2) passes through a membrane to combine with oxygen (O_2) from the air, producing the electricity that turns the wheels plus water vapor.

Configuration of Fuel cell hybrid electric vehicle (FCHEV)

Hydrogen Production

- ❖ Most hydrogen today is produced from fossil fuels (grey hydrogen).
- ❖ Clean methods (like electrolysis) are expensive and energy-intensive.
- ❖ **Recent Advancement:** Growing adoption of *green hydrogen* from renewable-powered electrolysis

Infrastructure Limitations

- ❖ Lack of hydrogen refueling stations (especially for longer commute vehicles more than 500km one side travelling distance).
- ❖ High cost and complexity in building distribution networks.
- ❖ **Recent Advancement:** Governments and companies (e.g., Shell, Toyota,Hyundai) investing in refueling infrastructure.
- ❖ Currently, India has only a handful of such stations, primarily located in a few cities. Expanding this infrastructure to cover the entire country is essential for the widespread adoption of hydrogen cars
- ❖ Safety is primary concern to storage outside the residential area.

Storage and Logistics

- ❖ Hydrogen is difficult to store due to its low density.
- ❖ Needs to be stored under high pressure or as a liquid – both require advanced technology and infrastructure and Budget
- ❖ **Recent initiation by Govt** Development of solid-state storage materials and metal hydrides for safer and compact storage.

Fuel Cell Cost and Durability

- ❖ Fuel cells use expensive materials (e.g., platinum catalysts).
- ❖ Degradation over time affects performance and reduce the life span.
- ❖ **Recent Advancement:** Use of non-platinum catalysts and improved membrane technology has extended lifespan and cut costs.

Vehicle Cost and Market Adoption

- ❖ Hydrogen cars (like Toyota Mirai) are more expensive than EVs or ICEs.
- ❖ Low production volumes = high unit costs.
- ❖ **Recent Advancement:** Hyundai and Toyota ramping up production to reduce costs through economies of scale
- ❖ In 2024, there's a predicted shift towards hydrogen in India. The National Green Hydrogen Mission aims to attract substantial investments for a 5 Million Metric Tons/year hydrogen production capacity. Market projections suggest a \$347.85 million hydrogen fuel cell vehicle market in India by 2030.
- ❖ By 2030, 15K hydrogen-powered Vehicles are expected, mainly for medium and heavy commercial vehicles.
- ❖ India's Car electrification is predicted to surpass China's and the USA's by 10-12%. The industry anticipates the introduction of green hydrogen-powered large vehicles on the road by 2028

Environmental & Policy Considerations

- ❖ Hydrogen production's environmental impact depends on the method.
- ❖ Need for stronger government Infrastructure, Approvals and incentives.
- ❖ **Recent Advancement: EU Hydrogen Strategy and U.S. Hydrogen Shot initiative to cut costs by 80% in a decade.**
- ❖ **Recognizing the potential of hydrogen as a clean energy source, the Indian government has taken several steps to promote hydrogen-based transportation. The National Hydrogen Energy Mission (NHEM), launched in 2021, aims to facilitate the development and deployment of hydrogen technologies across various sectors, including transportation.**
- ❖ **The government is conducting feasibility studies to check the potential of fuel-cell electric vehicles (FCEVs) in India. The current transport minister of India, Mr. Nitin Gadkari, has been actively advocating for hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs). He has even adopted a Toyota Mirai pilot study car as his daily mode of transportation.**
- ❖ **Our Transport minister of India, Mr. Nitin Gadkari is travelling with HFEV Toyota Camry as a Pilot project.**

Emerging Technologies and Innovations

- ❖ High-performance fuel cell stacks (Honda's next-gen FCX).
- ❖ Hydrogen internal combustion engines (ICEs) as an alternative under Development by Ashok leyland.
- ❖ Blending hydrogen with natural gas for hybrid powertrains.
- ❖ Autonomous hydrogen trucks (e.g., Nikola Motors(USA), Hyundai XCIENT(Korea)).

Conclusion & Future Outlook

- ❖ Hydrogen vehicles face major challenges in cost, infrastructure, and production.
- ❖ However, rapid advancements in technology and strong policy backing signal a promising future.
- ❖ **Future Vision:** Hydrogen as a key part of a multi-fuel ecosystem including EVs and Bi-fuels.